

Risk factors analysis of ASF in wild boar

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Abstract

Data on African Swine Fever (ASF) positive and negative reports in wild boar (*Sus scrofa*) were obtained for Latvia, Lithuania and Italy as the three target countries identified by EFSA. Additional data from Belgium and Sweden were also obtained. All these data were considered of suitable quality in terms of geo-location, but only data from Latvia and Lithuania were suitable for a full risk assessment, since data from the other locations were very tightly clustered, with data from Sweden and Italy to be used only in a single analysis. A list of potential risk factors was examined, but for several of them the spatial variability in the target countries was small, so they had to be excluded. Two statistical approaches were used to examine ASF occurrence and ASF persistence, respectively. The final models to explain the factors associated with ASF were reasonably good but could be hardly extrapolated across Europe, since some factors had limited variability within the target countries. For the occurrence model, the important factors to predict ASF were climatic (temperature and rainfall), with domestic pig density and wild boar density of only moderate importance in this scenario (Latvia and Lithuania). For ASF persistence similar climatic factors, along with various habitats were significant. Habitat features are difficult to summarise, as mosaic cropland (>50%), forest fragmentation and mosaic tree cover increase risk, but too much tree cover, cropland, water bodies and urban areas decrease risk. Domestic pig density and wild boar density were not important driving factors, although the latter could be due to the limited variation in the study area. Under the modelled scenario, our findings suggest that ASF in wild boar was not driven by a simple relationship with host presence or density, but in combination with habitat features that promote wild boar connectivity (such as a mosaic habitat) and a climate that promotes infectivity (of individuals or carcasses). We therefore strongly recommend that all ASF and in general all wildlife disease investigations are reported together with precise spatial data and that all negative reports are included, as this would vastly improve the ability to perform future analyses.

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Key words: wild boar, ASF, hunting bag, occurrence model, SDM, species distribution

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Summary

The spread of diseases such as African Swine Fever (ASF) among wild boar depends on many factors, including host density and distribution, habitat and climate. This analysis looks at factors associated with ASF reports in specified locations in Europe where suitable quality data are available. These countries identified by EFSA were Latvia, Lithuania and Italy, where positive and negative ASF laboratory results have been recorded with high geospatial precision. In addition, data from Sweden and Belgium were also obtained. Data from the local outbreaks in Italy, Belgium and Sweden were sparse and/or very clustered and were thus not generally suitable for model training. Further models utilised just the data from Latvia and Lithuania (except where stated). Initial modelling indicated that the very high rate of negative reports, compared to positives (14.8 times more data), was causing over-fitting, so the data were down sampled to match the number of positive cases.

A total of 85 environmental predictors were collated at a 2x2 km scale. These included estimated wild boar density data obtained from earlier ENETWILD analysis, climate, habitat and the presence of various scavengers. Of these initial variables many had to be excluded due to zero variance in the study region (31) or multicollinearity (17), leaving 37 predictor variables. Of these, a total of 23 were retained for the first model for ASF occurrence, as a further 14 had no importance in predicting ASF occurrence. A random forest model (presence/absence of ASF at any point during the time period) indicated that the most important factors included solar radiation, climate during certain quarters of the year and the presence of Eurasian Lynx (*Lynx lynx*). Density of domestic pigs had a moderate effect, but the predicted density of wild boar had the least importance. Some factors, such as altitude, had very limited variability in the study regions and the fact that all data were obtained from a small region of Europe meant that extrapolation of results to other parts of Europe may be problematic.

A second approach using data modified to account for the first recorded outbreak year per level 1 administrative region, using a condensed list of predictors (excluding scavenger information) was used to examine ASF occurrence. This model retained 39 of the original 85 predictors, included data from Sweden and Italy, and confirmed the importance of domestic pigs, altitude, forest fragmentation and some climatic variables (e.g. precipitation in the warmest quarter of the year; mean temperature of the wettest quarter) as important for ASF occurrence in wild boar. In this second model, estimated wild boar density became moderately important.

ASF persistence in wild boar (presence/absence of ASF positive carcasses per 4km² area) was examined by using a generalised additive model (GAM), which also identified Eurasian Lynx presence, similar climate factors to the occurrence model, and distance from roads as important. Persistence appears to be reduced in the presence of Lynx, and since many predators have limited European distributions, we suggest combined mammalian and avian predator variables are used in future persistence analyses. This could be a correlational finding mediated by ecological factors and management determining presence of lynx in low ASF risk areas and not a direct effect. A second linear model approach (consecutive quarters with presence of ASF-positive cases per 4 km² area) to examine persistence identified mostly different factors as important (the most significant included rainfall, temperature, connectivity, domestic pig density, forest fragmentation, and habitat cover), but confirmed that predicted initial wild boar density was not a driving factor for persistence in either approach.

We have to conclude that identifying and characterising factors that drive ASF persistence is challenging and not straightforward, and this may be due to the limited geographical extent of available data. ASF has been reported in wild boar in at least 18 European countries over the last few years, but this analysis has only been able to include data from a maximum of four countries (one single analysis could include data from Sweden and Italy). To perform any future analysis, it is fundamental that more countries report precise geo-locations for all positive and negative ASF reports since the time of the initial outbreak. This could help determining the riskiest areas for ASF spread and aid in the management of future outbreaks.

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1 Introduction

1.1 Background and terms of reference as provided by the requestor

This contract/grant was awarded by EFSA to: Università degli Studi di Torino (UNITO). Contract/Grant title: Wildlife and One Health: wildlife ecology, health surveillance and interaction with livestock, human population and environment, contract number: OC/EFSA/BIOHAW/2022/01.

The work package 4.1B of specific contract 01 of this framework contract was to perform a spatial statistical analysis of the risk factors involved in ASF epidemiology in wild boar scenarios previously identified, including wild boar density.

1.2 Scope of the report

The Commission needs regular updated epidemiological analysis of the ASF evolution, based on the data collected from the Member States affected by ASFV Genotype II. In addition, updated insights on the risk factors involved in ASF introduction into new territories, disease spread and persistence in Europe are required to be able to update the disease prevention, control, and management policies. EFSA has received the mandate from the Commission to provide technical and scientific assistance to review, identify and describe risk factors involved in the occurrence, spread and persistence of the ASF virus in the wild boar population, with a view to inform risk management and enable the preparation of future risk assessment mandates. The analyses should consider the knowledge acquired in previous EFSA opinions and scientific reports on ASF. The analyses will be based on data collected by Member States and submitted to the EFSA Data Collection Framework on ASF surveillance. Also, existing mechanism to estimate the wild boar population data should be also employed in the analyses. Also, EFSA is requested to draft two scientific reports using those data and additional sources of information, as well as expert elicitations (e.g., *ENETWILD* consortium), with the support of the EFSA Working Group of experts on ASF (WG). The first risk factor report by EFSA should include the identification of new scientific evidence on the risk factors involved in the occurrence, spread and maintenance of ASF virus, as well as including wild boar density.

2 Data and Methods

2.1 ASF Data

A total of 293,512 ASF screening records were obtained for Latvia, Lithuania, Italy, Sweden, and Belgium, provided by contacts at EFSA, WAHIS, and external research groups (see Table 1 for breakdown of number of ASF-positive cases and ASF-negative reports, and the year of the earliest and latest record for each country). Throughout, we restrict the use of ASF-cases to wild boar carcasses that test positive for ASF. We refer to carcasses that are tested negative as ASF-negative reports, and the total data set as ASF reports. The data may come from found dead, roadkill or hunted animals.

Table 1 – Summary table showing the number of ASF-cases and ASF-negative reports, recorded in Latvia, Lithuania, Italy, Sweden, and Belgium, along with the year for the earliest and latest record.

Country	Number of ASF- Cases	Number of ASF-Negative Reports	Year of Earliest Record	Year of Latest Record
Latvia	4,972	114,938	2014	2024
Lithuania	6,782	152,304	2015	2023
Italy	321	8,981	2022	2023
Sweden	60	466	2014	2024
Belgium	4,376	312	2018	2021

Note: ASF-cases were determined based on polymerase chain reaction (PCR) diagnostic testing.

2.2 Methods

Modelling of ASF reports in Europe was conducted in R (version 4.2.2; R Core Team, 2022), using the RStudio interactive development environment (IDE; version 2022.12.0; Posit team, 2022).

Despite data being provided for all countries of interest, modelling was conducted on data pertaining to Latvia and Lithuania only. This was due to the long-term presence of ASF in both countries, as evidence by the temporal distribution of records, as well as large-scale screening of wild boar, resulting in national coverage of ASF presence/absence records (see Figure 1 a–d for geographical distributions of records). By comparison, ASF cases in Italy, Sweden and Belgium were either recent (e.g. Italy and Sweden), numerically sparse (e.g. Sweden), or exhibited regional clustering (i.e. outbreak hotspots consistent across all three countries; see Figure 2 a – f for geographical distributions of records).

ASF Status

- 0
- 1

Figure 1a – d. Maps of Latvia (top) and Lithuania (bottom) showing the geographic distribution of ASF-cases (a and c) and ASF-negative reports (b and d) in wild boar (*Sus scrofa*). ASF reports are taken over a range of years (Latvia = 2014 – 2024; Lithuania = 2015 – 2023).

ASF Status

- 0
- 1

a)

b)

c)

d)

e)

f)

Figure 2a – f. Maps of Italy (top panels), Sweden (middle panels) and Belgium (bottom panels) showing the geographic distribution of ASF-cases (a, c and e) and ASF-negative reports (b, d, and f) in wild boar (*Sus scrofa*). ASF-reports are taken over a range of years (Italy = 2022 – 2023; Sweden = 2014 – 2024; Belgium = 2018 – 2021).

Having selected the regions of interest, corresponding ASF report data were processed to ensure that only a single point record was present within any 2 x 2 km (4 km²) area. The selected grid size (4 km²) aligns (in terms of spatial scale) with the minimum range of the spatial behaviour (home range) of wild boar in Europe (ENETWILD-consortium et al 2022).

Where both ASF-cases and ASF-negative reports occurred in the same 4 km² area, priority was given to the ASF- case. This resulted in a total of 1,505 ASF- cases, and 22,334 ASF-negative reports, recorded across Latvia and Lithuania. Given the 14.8-fold difference in the number of ASF-cases and ASF-negative reports, initial runs of the ASF occurrence model revealed substantial over-fitting, particularly for the most abundant infection status (i.e. ASF-negative). When predicting ASF-negative reports, the ASF occurrence model generated a classification error rate of 0.05%, whereas for ASF-positive cases, an error rate of 99.25% was produced. Therefore, further filtering of the data was performed, with ASF-negative reports randomly down-sampled to match the number of ASF-cases; a procedure that has been recommended as an appropriate solution to class imbalance when modelling the distribution of species (see Benkendorf et al., 2023). This procedure resulted in a final dataset comprising of 1,505 data records for ASF-cases and ASF-negative reports respectively (n = 3,010 records total).

Environmental Predictors of ASF

A total of 85 environmental predictors were initially selected for inclusion in models (see Table 2 for descriptions). These predictors were selected based on previous studies, such as the

review conducted by Bergmann et al. (2022), or previous ENETWILD studies (ENETWILD-consortium et al. 2024).

Where required, data for environmental predictors was standardised to a format that was applicable to our modelling framework. Environmental predictors were provided in the form of raster layers covering the full extent of Europe, at a resolution of 2 x 2 km. All raster datasets were set with the EPGS 3035 projected coordinate reference system (ETRS89-extended/ LAEA Europe).

Table 2. The full set of potential predictors used in the occurrence models. Those retained in the first occurrence model are highlighted in bold.

Type of Predictor	Predictor Name	Description	Source
Wild boar related	connectivity_distance	Distance to nearest grid cell with known wild boar presence (km)	ENETWILD
	density	Density of Wild Boar (individuals/km²)	ENETWILD
	presence ³	Wild boar presence (categorical)	ENETWILD
	range ¹	Range of stable long-term populations	ENETWILD
	Suitability ³	Suitability for Wild Boar	ENETWILD
Spatial	bioregion ¹	Bioclimatic regionalisation	ENETWILD
Climate	bio1 ²	Annual Mean Temperature (°C)	Worldclim
	bio2 ²	Annual Mean Diurnal Range (°C)	Worldclim
	bio3	Isothermality (%): areas with relative constant temperature	Worldclim
	bio4 ²	Temperature Seasonality – Standard Deviation (°C)	Worldclim
	bio5 ²	Maximum Temperature of Warmest Month (°C)	Worldclim
	bio6 ²	Minimum Temperature of Coldest Month (°C)	Worldclim
	bio7 ²	Annual Temperature Range (°C)	Worldclim
	bio8	Mean Temperature of Wettest Quarter (°C)	Worldclim
	bio9	Mean Temperature of Driest Quarter (°C)	Worldclim
	bio10	Mean Temperature of Warmest Quarter (°C)	Worldclim
	bio11 ²	Mean Temperature of Coldest Quarter (°C)	Worldclim
	bio12 ²	Annual Precipitation (mm)	Worldclim
	bio13 ²	Precipitation of Wettest Month (mm)	Worldclim

	bio14 ²	Precipitation of Driest Month (mm)	Worldclim
	bio15	Precipitation Seasonality – CV (%)	Worldclim
	bio16 ²	Precipitation of Wettest Quarter (mm)	Worldclim
	bio17 ²	Precipitation of Driest Quarter (mm)	Worldclim
	bio18	Precipitation of Warmest Quarter (mm)	Worldclim
	bio19 ²	Precipitation of Coldest Quarter (mm)	Worldclim
	grow ³	Length of Vegetation Growing Period	Food and Agricultural Organisation of the United Nations (FAO)
	snow ²	Snow cover	Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer project (MODIS)
	sun	Sun radiation inferred from latitude, slope, orientation.	Worldclim
Domestic Hosts	DA_PigDensity	Domestic Pig Density – Dasymetric method (2015)	Food and Agricultural Organisation of the United Nations (FAO)
Environment (Habitat)	alt	Mean Altitude	United States Geological Survey (USGS)
	lc10 ^e	Cropland (rainfed)	European Space Agency (ESA)
	lc11	Herbaceous cover	European Space Agency (ESA)
	lc12 ³	Tree or shrub cover	European Space Agency (ESA)
	lc20 ¹	Cropland, irrigated or post-flooding	European Space Agency (ESA)
	lc30	Mosaic cropland (>50%) / natural vegetation (tree, shrub, herbaceous cover) (<50%)	European Space Agency (ESA)
	lc40 ³	Mosaic natural vegetation (tree, shrub, herbaceous cover) (>50%) / cropland (<50%)	European Space Agency (ESA)
	lc60	Tree cover, broad-leaved, deciduous, closed to open (>15%)	European Space Agency (ESA)

	lc61 ³	Tree cover, broad-leaved, deciduous, closed (>40%)	European Space Agency (ESA)
	lc70 ²	Tree cover, needle leaved, evergreen, closed to open (>15%)	European Space Agency (ESA)
	lc71 ¹	Tree cover, needle leaved, evergreen, closed (>40%)	European Space Agency (ESA)
	lc80 ³	Tree cover, needle leaved, deciduous, closed to open (>15%)	European Space Agency (ESA)
	lc90	Tree cover, mixed leaf type (broadleaved and needle leaved)	European Space Agency (ESA)
	lc100 ³	Mosaic tree and shrub (>50%) / herbaceous cover (<50%)	European Space Agency (ESA)
	lc110 ³	Mosaic herbaceous cover (>50%) / tree and shrub (<50%)	European Space Agency (ESA)
	lc120 ¹	Shrubland	European Space Agency (ESA)
	lc122 ¹	Deciduous shrubland	European Space Agency (ESA)
	lc130 ³	Grassland	European Space Agency (ESA)
	lc150 ³	Sparse vegetation (tree, shrub, herbaceous cover) (<15%)	European Space Agency (ESA)
	lc152 ¹	Sparse shrub (<15%)	European Space Agency (ESA)
	lc153 ¹	Sparse herbaceous cover (<15%)	European Space Agency (ESA)
	lc160 ¹	Tree cover, flooded, fresh or brackish water	European Space Agency (ESA)
	lc180	Shrub or herbaceous cover, flooded, fresh/saline/brackish water	European Space Agency (ESA)
	lc200 ¹	Bare areas	European Space Agency (ESA)
	lc201 ¹	Consolidated bare areas	European Space Agency (ESA)
	lc202 ¹	Unconsolidated bare areas	European Space Agency (ESA)
Environment – Potential Barriers Environment	ffi	Forest fragmentation index	Ma et al. (2023)
	hfp	Human Footprint Index	Socioeconomic Data and Applications Center (SEDAC)
	lc190 ³	Urban areas	European Space Agency (ESA)

	Ic210 ³	Water bodies	European Space Agency (ESA)
	Ic220 ¹	Permanent snow and ice	European Space Agency (ESA)
	road_distance	Distance in km to the nearest road	European Environment Agency (EEA)
Landscape Change	arable_change	Arable land and permanent crop cover change (2000 – 2018)	European Environment Agency (EEA)
	forest_change	Forest land cover change (2000 – 2018)	European Environment Agency (EEA)
Scavenger Community	AgMPresenc ¹	Presence of <i>Aegypius monachus</i> Cinereous vulture	International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN)
	AqAPresenc ¹	Presence of <i>Aquila adalberti</i> Spanish imperial eagle	International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN)
	AqCPresenc ²	Presence of <i>Aquila chrysaetos</i> Golden eagle	International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN)
	AqFPresenc ¹	Presence of <i>Aquila fasciatus</i> Bonelli's eagle	International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN)
	BtBPresenc ¹	Presence of <i>Buteo buteo</i> Common buzzard	International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN)
	CnLPresenc ¹	Presence of <i>Canis lupis</i> wolf	International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN)
	CrCPresenc ¹	Presence of <i>Corvus corax</i> Common raven	International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN)
	CrNPresenc ¹	Presence of <i>Corvus corone</i> Carrion crow	International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN)
	GuGPresenc ¹	Presence of <i>Gulo gulo</i> wolverine	International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN)
	GyBPresenc ¹	Presence of <i>Gypaetus barbatus</i> Bearded vulture	International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN)
	GyFPresenc ¹	Presence of <i>Gyps fulvus</i> Eurasian griffon vulture	International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN)
	HIAPresenc ¹	Presence of <i>Haliaeetus leucocephalus</i> Bald eagle	International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN)
	LyLPresenc	Presence of <i>Lynx lynx</i> Eurasian lynx	International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN)

	LyPPresenc ¹	Presence of <i>Lynx pardinus</i> Iberian Lynx	International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN)
	MeMPresenc ¹	Presence of <i>Meles meles</i> badger	International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN)
	MvMPresenc ¹	Presence of <i>Milvus migrans</i> Black kite	International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN)
	NpPPresenc ¹	Presence of <i>Neophron percnopterus</i> Egyptian <i>vulture</i>	International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN)
	NyPPresenc ¹	Presence of <i>Nyctereutes procyonoides</i> Raccoon dog	International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN)
	SuSPresenc ¹	Presence of Wild boar (<i>Sus scrofa</i>)	International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN)
	UrAPresenc	Presence of <i>Ursus arctos</i> Brown bear	International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN)
	VuVPresenc ¹	Presence of red fox (<i>Vulpes vulpes</i>)	International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN)
	scvRich ²	Number of scavenger species	Mateo-Tomás et al 2015

Note: Numerical superscripts denote the following:

¹ Removal of environmental predictors based on zero-variance characteristics for Latvia and Lithuania.

² Removal of environmental predictors based on variable inflation factor (VIF).

³ Removal of environmental predictors based on permutation importance.

Of the 85 initially selected environmental predictors, 31 were subsequently excluded given that each exhibited zero variance when cropped to only consider the study region (i.e. Latvia and Lithuania). The remaining 54 variables were further evaluated for issues regarding multicollinearity, caused by multiple independent predictors correlating with one another. Using the sub-setted ASF dataset, estimates were extracted for each predictor variable, from their respective raster layers, and assessed using the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF), which quantifies the amount of inflation the variance of a given variable experiences relative to others (indicating multicollinearity). All 54 predictors were assessed by using the *flexsdm::correct_colinvar* function (version 1.3.4; Velazco et al., 2022) and applying a VIF threshold of 5, which represents a moderate level of multicollinearity (see Marcoulides & Raykov, 2019). When applied, VIF testing revealed that 17 predictors exhibited multicollinearity, and were therefore removed, leaving 37 remaining predictor variables.

Those remaining predictors were then further assessed, to determine their overall importance in predicting the occurrence of ASF. Assessment was performed using permutation variable importance, a method which measures the contribution of a given variable, when permuted, in increasing the prediction error (and therefore performance) of a model. This process was

performed using the *Boruta::Boruta* function (version 8.0.0; Kursa & Rudnicki, 2010), with a 99% significance level ($\alpha = 0.01$), and a total run of 500 permutations per variable. Importance was determined using the default method, which gathers Z-scores of mean decrease in model accuracy. Permutation variable importance revealed a further 14 predictors as having little to no importance in predicting the occurrence of ASF, and as such were removed, leaving 23 variables for inclusion in the ASF occurrence model (Table 2 in bold).

2.2.1 Model Fitting – Occurrence (1)

The modelling of ASF occurrence data, in relation to environmental predictors, was performed using a random forest machine learning model (*randomForest::randomForest*; version 4.7-1.1; Liaw & Wiener, 2002). When compared to other machine-learning models (e.g. neural network), random forest models are able to handle datasets consisting of a large number of predictors, with a comparatively lower associated cost when evaluating the importance or contribution of each predictor variable (Speiser et al., 2019). This was a classification model, in which ASF infection status was provided as a binary factor (0 = ASF-negative, 1 = ASF-positive). Lynx and bear presence (*LyLPresenc* and *UrAPresenc*), were both fitted as binary factors (0 = absent, 1 = present), whilst the remaining predictors were fitted as numerical predictors. The random forest model was set to simulate a total of 500 decision “trees”, a number sufficient to stabilise model errors, with each tree node (i.e. the point at which decision trees split), set at the recommended default value (the square-root for the total number of predictor variables; $n = 5$).

The random forest model was initially trained using a subset of the final dataset, comprising of 80% of all records (i.e. the training dataset). The remaining 20% was retained for model validation (i.e. the test dataset). Partitioning of the training and testing datasets was performed using block cross-validation, with the dataset partitioned into 5 independent folds. Partitioning was performed systematically using the *blockCV::cv_spatial* function (version 3.1-3; Valavi et al., 2019), with training and testing data selected based on geographical separation. A total distance for each block was set at 60km² – representing the dispersal range of wild boar (Santini et al., 2013). To ensure that partitions were evenly dispersed, partitioning was conducted over a total of 50 iterations.

For each run of the 5-fold cross validation process, model performance was evaluated using two common metrics; 1) Area Under the Curve (AUC), which evaluates model performance by comparing the true positive rate (sensitivity) against the false positive rate (1 – true negative rate; specificity), with a value of 1 representing perfect classification and 0.5 as random classification, and 2) True Skill Statistic (TSS), which evaluates model performance by comparing true positive rates (TPR; sensitivity) against true negative rates (TNR; specificity), and is calculated as $TSS = TPR + TNR - 1$. A TSS score of -1 is indicative of poor performance (worse than chance), 1 is indicative of perfect classification, and 0 represents random classification. From there, the random forest model was then used to predict the probability of ASF occurrence in Latvia and Lithuania.

2.2.2 Model Fitting – Occurrence (2)

For the second round of analyses, ASF data were further refined. For each country of interest (Latvia, Lithuania, Sweden, Italy, and Belgium), an updated dataset of ASF-cases and ASF-negative reports was compiled ($n = 327,559$ data points), and then filtered based on both

spatial and temporal extent. Using the Database of Global Administrative Areas (GADM), information regarding the State, Province, or equivalent administrative region (referred to as Administrative Level 1; <https://gadm.org/>) was extracted for each record, based on recorded geospatial coordinates. For each country, data was filtered to only consider records collected on, or after the first reported outbreak year, ignoring years with very limited data (Latvia \geq 2015, Lithuania \geq 2016, Italy \geq 2022, Sweden \geq 2023 and Belgium \geq 2018). This resulted in a dataset consisting of 323,313 records, with 120,299 records obtained for Latvia, 160,237 records for Lithuania, 37,584 records for Italy, 313 records for Sweden, and 4,880 records for Belgium.

For the ASF occurrence model, ASF data underwent further spatial filtering so that, for each level 1 administrative region, only the earliest ASF-cases and ASF-negative reports were retained. This resulted in a dataset consisting of 29,448 records, of which 1,779 records were retained for Latvia, 15,010 records for Lithuania, 11,684 records for Italy, 243 records for Sweden, and 732 records for Belgium. At this stage, Belgium was subsequently removed from the dataset, given the highly clustered nature of ASF-positive cases when compared to other countries of interest, resulting in a dataset consisting of 28,716 records from Latvia, Lithuania, Sweden and Italy.

Records were further filtered to only include data which fell within a pre-defined calibration area. This option was selected to avoid issues which might manifest due to the widespread distribution of ASF-negative reports in some countries (e.g. Latvia and Lithuania), which could cause a bias within the model, when trying to predict the presence/absence of ASF. For each ASF-positive record, a 10km calibration buffer was generated to reflect previous estimates of average ranging patterns in wild boar in Europe (see Keuling et al., 2010). These multiple calibration areas were dissolved to form a single mask object, with which ASF-negative records were filtered. Those ASF-negative records, which occurred within the calibration area, were retained, whilst those outside were excluded.

ASF data were then processed to ensure that only a single point record was present within any 2 x 2 km cell, with ASF- cases given priority over ASF-negative in the event of co-occurrence within the same cell. This resulted in a final dataset consisting of 2,002 records (675 ASF-positive cells: 1,327 ASF-negative cells).

Based on comments provided by the ENETWILD working group, the ASF occurrence model was repeated using a condensed list of potential risk factors, by excluding those factors which related to scavenger presence and/or richness, thus resulting in 63 risk variables that were further refined to exclude any variables which exhibited zero-variance, based on estimates extracted using the ASF dataset. Risk variables were also assessed for multicollinearity, with any variable exhibiting a VIF score $>$ 5 being excluded. This resulted in a final list consisting of 37 potential risk variables (see Table 3).

Table 3. The 37 predictors used in the second occurrence model.

Type of Predictor	Predictor Name	Description	Source
Wild boar-related	connectivity_distance	Distance to nearest grid cell with known wild boar presence (km)	ENETWILD
	density	Density of Wild Boar (individuals/km ²)	ENETWILD

	presence	Wild boar presence (categorical)	ENETWILD
	range	Range of stable long-term populations	ENETWILD
	suitability	Suitability for Wild Boar	ENETWILD
Spatial	bioregion	Bioclimatic regionalisation	ENETWILD
	bio2	Annual Mean Diurnal Range (°C)	Worldclim
	bio8	Mean Temperature of Wettest Quarter (°C)	Worldclim
	bio15	Precipitation Seasonality - CV (%)	Worldclim
	bio18	Precipitation of Warmest Quarter (mm)	Worldclim
Domestic Hosts	DA_PigDensity	Domestic Pig Density - Dasymetric method (2015)	Food and Agricultural Organisation of the United Nations (FAO)
Environment (Habitat)	alt	Mean Altitude	United States Geological Survey (USGS)
	lc10	Cropland (rainfed)	European Space Agency (ESA)
	lc11	Herbaceous cover	European Space Agency (ESA)
	lc12	Tree or shrub cover	European Space Agency (ESA)
	lc20	Cropland, irrigated or post-flooding	European Space Agency (ESA)
	lc30	Mosaic cropland (>50%) / natural vegetation (tree, shrub, herbaceous cover) (<50%)	European Space Agency (ESA)
	lc40	Mosaic natural vegetation (tree, shrub, herbaceous cover) (>50%) / cropland (<50%)	European Space Agency (ESA)
	lc61	Tree cover, broad-leaved, deciduous, closed (>40%)	European Space Agency (ESA)
	lc70	Tree cover, needle leaved, evergreen, closed to open (>15%)	European Space Agency (ESA)
	lc80	Tree cover, needle leaved, deciduous, closed to open (>15%)	European Space Agency (ESA)
	lc90	Tree cover, mixed leaf type (broadleaved and needle leaved)	European Space Agency (ESA)
	lc100	Mosaic tree and shrub (>50%) / herbaceous cover (<50%)	European Space Agency (ESA)

	lc110	Mosaic herbaceous cover (>50%) / tree and shrub (<50%)	European Space Agency (ESA)
	lc120	Shrubland	European Space Agency (ESA)
	lc130	Grassland	European Space Agency (ESA)
	lc150	Sparse vegetation (tree, shrub, herbaceous cover) (<15%)	European Space Agency (ESA)
	lc180	Shrub or herbaceous cover, flooded, fresh/saline/brackish water	European Space Agency (ESA)
	lc200	Bare areas	European Space Agency (ESA)
	lc202	Unconsolidated bare areas	European Space Agency (ESA)
Environment – Potential Barriers Environment	ffi	Forest fragmentation index	Ma et al. (2023)
	hfp	Human Footprint Index	Socioeconomic Data and Applications Center (SEDAC)
	lc190	Urban areas	European Space Agency (ESA)
	lc210	Water bodies	European Space Agency (ESA)
	road_distance	Distance in km to the nearest road	European Environment Agency (EEA)
Landscape Change	arable_change	Arable land and permanent crop cover change (2000 – 2018)	European Environment Agency (EEA)
	forest_change	Forest land cover change (2000 – 2018)	European Environment Agency (EEA)

Following the previous iteration of the ASF occurrence model, a random forest machine learning model was fitted to assess the effect of potential risk factors in predicting ASF occurrence. Using permutation variable importance, and the criteria described initially (see above), the model was also assessed to determine the relative importance of each risk variable, in predicting ASF occurrence.

2.2.3 Model Fitting – Persistence (1)

Unlike the ASF occurrence model, in which probability of ASF presence was partially dependent on the spatial distribution of records, with a higher probability of occurrence attributable to regions in which a higher frequency of ASF-cases was found, the purpose of

the ASF persistence model was to consider the impact of ASF-suitability, in conjunction with environmental predictors, in the absence of spatial effects.

As such, rather than estimating a probability based on the environmental conditions of a given cell, and cells within the surrounding neighbourhood, the persistence model aimed to estimate probability based solely on environmental conditions. This could be regarded as one metric demonstrating how difficult disease eradication may be.

We performed spatially thinning on the final dataset used in the ASF occurrence model, consisting of 1,505 ASF-cases and 1,505 ASF-negative reports. Spatial thinning was performed using the *spThin::thin* function (version 0.2.0; Aiello-Lammens et al., 2015), which utilises a randomisation algorithm to generate a subsetted dataset, in which all data points are a minimum distance from one another. We assigned a minimum distance of 10km to reflect previous estimates of average ranging patterns in wild boar in Europe (see Keuling et al., 2010). This randomised thinning process was conducted 100 times and the resulting dataset, which contained the greatest number of datapoints was selected. Spatial thinning was performed on ASF-cases and ASF-negative data separately, to ensure no potential bias. The resulting dataset consisted of 456 ASF-cases and 564 ASF-negative reports.

The ASF persistence model was conducted using a generalised additive model (GAM), a close relative to the generalised linear model (GLM). However, unlike the GLM, in which relationships between the response variable and predictors are assumed to be linear, the GAM can account for non-linear relationships by applying a smoothing term(s), thereby offering a more flexible, and generalised option for regression analysis. Using the *mgcv::gam* function (version 1.8-41; Wood, 2011), a GAM was fitted with a binomial error distribution and a logistic link function. As with the ASF occurrence model, the response variable was ASF infection status, provided as a binary 0/1 (ASF-negative/ASF-case), and the list of predictors consisted of the same 23 variables, along with the probability of ASF occurrence (ASF_Suitability) – a product of the first model. Excluding those predictors which were categorical (LyLPresenc and UrAPresenc), all continuous predictors were fitted with the default thin-plate smoothing function. The GAM was further modified to include an intrinsic selection process, thereby allowing those predictors, predicted to have little to no effect on the response variable, to be penalised to zero, effectively removing them from the model. Once fitted, the GAM was evaluated to ensure that smoothing of continuous predictors was reasonable. In the event of a problematic fit, these smoothing functions were further penalised to improve model fit.

The resulting GAM was then used to predict the probability of ASF persistence across the full extent of Latvia and Lithuania.

2.2.4 Model Fitting – Persistence (2)

ASF persistence was re-assessed to account for the effect of temporal variations on ASF occurrence, and the risk factors that might contribute to the prolonged presence of ASF outbreaks within a region. As with the previous version of the ASF persistence model, our analysis focussed primarily on Latvia and Lithuania, given that the ASF outbreaks in Italy, Belgium and Sweden have been subject to strict control. As such, Latvia and Lithuania are the only countries with the longest, most consistent records of ASF occurrence, across all

countries where we have data. Returning to the original dataset, filtered so that the data began at the first outbreak year for each country ($n = 323,313$ records), further refinements were made to focus on Latvia and Lithuania only, producing a dataset consisting of 280,536 records. These records were then filtered, to only include ASF-cases. Unlike the previous model, in which persistence was determined from ASF-positive and ASF-negative data, the current model only considered ASF-cases, aggregated to a spatial resolution of 4km^2 . Using the environmental raster predictor data, clipped to both Latvia and Lithuania, ASF-positive data were summarised per 4km^2 grid cell, generating an absolute count of positive records. This process was sub-divided into quarterly periods, covering 8 years (32 quarter-years in total). Having generated counts of ASF-positive cases per 4km^2 area, this data was further summarised, to determine the greatest number of consecutive quarters, in which an ASF positive was found, thus accounting for time of persistence.

This dataset was then further modified to include data pertaining to the initial 63 variables identified in our secondary analyses.

As with the ASF occurrence model, risk variables were assessed for zero-variance and multicollinearity, resulting in 14 variables being removed. The final dataset consisted of 51,211 data rows, with data corresponding to the following risk factors: 1) alt, 2) arable_change, 3) bio3, 4) bio8, 5) bio9, 6) bio10, 7) bio13, 8) bio15, 9) connectivity_distance, 10) DA_PigDensity, 11) density, 12) ffi, 13) forest_change, 14) grow, 15) hfp, 16) lc10, 17) lc11, 18) lc12, 19) lc30, 20) lc40, 21) lc60, 22) lc61, 23) lc71, 24) lc80, 25) lc90, 26) lc100, 27) lc110, 28) lc130, 29) lc150, 30) lc150, 31) lc180, 32) lc190, 33) lc202, 34) lc210, 35) presence, 36) range, 37) road_distance, 38) suitability and 39) sun.

Unlike the previous ASF persistence model, which utilised a generalised additive model, the current model consisted of a simple generalised linear model, fitted with a Poisson error distribution. The decision to use a standard generalised linear model was based on the now simplified assumption regarding temporal change (i.e. number of consecutive quarters), and the elimination of any spatial components. All risk variables were considered as main effects only. Where possible, model simplification was performed, to remove non-significant predictors. Any simplification that was performed, was assessed against the previous model structure, to determine if variable removal improved or worsened model fit. This was performed by assessing changes in residual deviance using a Chi-square test.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1.1 Occurrence (1)

Evaluation of the random forest classification model produced an average AUC score of 0.704, and a TSS score of 0.500, indicating that model performance was fair. An examination of each validation fold revealed that performance remained, on average, relatively consistent (fold 1: AUC = 0.697, TSS = 0.483; fold 2: AUC = 0.709, TSS = 0.497; fold 3: AUC = 0.693, TSS = 0.497; fold 4: AUC = 0.709, TSS = 0.484; fold 5: AUC = 0.710, TSS = 0.540).

A closer examination of each predictor's contribution to model performance showed that inclusion of solar radiation (sun), precipitation of warmest quarter (bio18) and mean temperature of wettest quarter (bio8) had the greatest effect upon model accuracy, whereas

wild boar density (density), the percentage of mixed leaf tree cover (lc90), and the percentage cover of mosaic cropland (lc30), had the least (see Table 4 for ranked summary). This trend was confirmed based on partial dependence plots (see Figure 3a – w). For many of these predictors the effect of each was small, as indicated by the scale in the y-axis.

Table 4. Estimated mean contribution of each environmental predictor in predicting the probability of ASF occurrence in Latvia and Lithuania, generated using a random forest classification model. Contribution is measured based on the mean decrease in model accuracy, following the permuted removal of a given predictor when growing simulated trees.

Predictor	Contribution to Model Accuracy
Sun: Sun radiation	25.35
bio18: Precipitation of Warmest Quarter	19.66
bio8: Mean Temperature of Wettest Quarter	17.42
bio15: Precipitation Seasonality – CV	17.20
bio9: Mean Temperature of Driest Quarter	16.88
LyLPresenc: Presence of Eurasian lynx	16.27
bio10: Mean Temperature of Warmest Quarter	15.82
DA_PigDensity: Domestic Pig Density	15.15
bio3: Isothermality	14.42
Alt: Mean Altitude	14.04
connectivity_distance: Distance to nearest grid cell with known wild boar presence	13.87
Ffi: Forest fragmentation index	13.53
arable_change: Arable land and permanent crop cover change (2000 – 2018)	9.98
forest_change: Forest land cover change (2000–2018)	8.11
hfp: Human Footprint Index	8.02
road_distance: Distance in km to the nearest road	7.78
UrAPresenc: Presence of Brown bear	7.47
lc60: Tree cover, broad-leaved, deciduous, closed to open (>15%)	6.82
lc11: Herbaceous cover	6.26
lc30: Mosaic cropland (>50%)	5.97
lc90: Tree cover, mixed leaf type (broadleaved and needle leaved)	5.87
Density: Density of Wild Boar	2.31
lc180: Shrub or herbaceous cover, flooded, fresh/saline/brackish water	8.52

a Mean Altitude

b Arable land and permanent crop cover change

c Isothermality

d Mean Temperature of Wettest Quarter

e Mean Temperature of Driest Quarter

f Mean Temperature of Warmest Quarter

g Precipitation Seasonality – CV

h Precipitation of Warmest Quarter

i Distance to nearest grid cell with known wild boar presence j Domestic Pig Density

k Density of Wild Boar

l Forest fragmentation index

m Forest land cover change

n Human Footprint Index

o %age herbaceous cover

p %age mosaic cropland / natural vegetation

q %age tree cover, broad-leaved, deciduous, closed to open

r %age tree cover, mixed leaf type

s %age shrub or herbaceous cover, flooded, fresh/saline/brackish water

t Presence of Lynx

u Distance to the nearest road

v Sun radiation

w Presence of bear

Figure 3a – w. Partial dependence plots showing the effect that each of the 23 predictor variables is predicted to have on the probability of ASF occurring in a given region, based on ASF records compiled for Latvia and Lithuania between 2014 and 2024. Predictors selected for use in the ASF occurrence model are as follows: a) alt, b) arable_change, c) bio3, d) bio8, e) bio9, f) bio10, g) bio15, h) bio18, i) connectivity_distance, j) DA_PigDensity, k) density, l) ffi, m) forest_change, n) hfp, o) lc11, p) lc30, q) lc60, r) lc90, s) lc180, t) LyLPresenc, u) road_distance, v) sun, and w) UrAPresenc. Please refer to Table 2 for descriptions regarding each of the selected predictors.

Having been trained using data obtained for Latvia and Lithuania, the model visually appeared to perform relatively well when projecting to the national level (see Figure 4a, b).

a

b

Figure 4. Modelled probability of occurrence of ASF in (a) Latvia and (b) Lithuania. The low values (purple) are consistent with areas of less ASF cases (insets show the positive cases from Figure 1).

3.1.2 Occurrence (2)

Repeating the ASF occurrence model using a modified dataset, filtered based on first outbreak year per level 1 administrative region, and with a 10km calibration area around ASF-positive cases, revealed a model whose model performance was fair (mean AUC = 0.84; average TSS = 0.40).

Using permutation variable importance, a total of 25 variables were identified as important when predicting ASF occurrence, including; alt (mean altitude); arable change (permanent crop cover change 2000-2018); bio2 (annual mean diurnal temperature range); bio8 (mean temperature of wettest quarter); bio15 (variation in precipitation); bio18 (precipitation in warmest quarter); bioregion; connectivity distance (distance to known wild boar); DA_PigDensity (domestic pig density); density (wild boar density); ffi (forest fragmentation); forest change; hfp (human footprint index); lc10 (cropland); lc11 (herbaceous cover); lc12 (tree/ shrub cover); lc30 (mosaic cropland); lc40 (mosaic natural vegetation); lc70 (evergreen tree cover); lc90 (mixed tree/shrub cover); lc100 (mosaic tree/shrub cover); lc130

(grassland); lc190 (urban areas); road_distance (distance to nearest road); suitability (for wild boar – ENETWILD).

A closer examination of each predictor's contribution to model performance showed that those variables that related to temperature (bio2 and bio8), and precipitation (bio15 and bio18) had the greatest effect upon model accuracy, whereas habitat connectivity (connectivity_distance), habitat suitability for wild boar (suitability), and proximity to roads (road_distance) had the least (see Table 5 for ranked summary). This trend was confirmed based on partial dependence plots (see Figure 5a – y). For many of these predictors the effect of each was small, as indicated by the scale in the y-axis.

Table 5. Estimated mean contribution of each environmental predictor in predicting the probability of ASF occurrence in Latvia and Lithuania, generated using a random forest classification model. Contribution is measured based on the mean decrease in model accuracy, following the permuted removal of a given predictor when growing simulated trees.

Predictor	Contribution to Model Accuracy
bio18: Precipitation of Warmest Quarter	32.72
bio2: Annual Mean Diurnal Range °C	31.49
bio8: Mean Temperature of Wettest Quarter	29.99
bio15: Precipitation Seasonality	22.22
Ffi: Forest fragmentation index	20.60
Alt: Mean Altitude	19.19
Hfp: Human Footprint Index	15.25
forest_change: Forest land cover change (2000 – 2018)	14.59
lc11: Herbaceous cover	13.00
Density: Density of Wild Boar	12.80
DA_PIGDENSITY: Domestic Pig Density	12.42
lc12: Tree or shrub cover	10.12
arable_change	8.34
lc40: Mosaic natural vegetation (>50%)	8.33
lc90: Tree cover, mixed leaf	8.17
lc130: Grassland	8.16
lc100: Mosaic tree and shrub (>50%)	7.50
bioregion	7.49
lc70: Tree cover, needle leaved (>15%)	6.89
lc10: Cropland	6.09
lc30: Mosaic cropland (>50%)	6.05
lc190: Urban areas	6.00
road_distance: Distance to the nearest road	4.75
Suitability: Suitability for Wild Boar	4.01

connectivity_distance: Distance to nearest grid cell with wild boar	3.93
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a Precipitation of Warmest Quarter

b Annual Mean Diurnal Range

c Mean Temperature of Wettest Quarter

d Precipitation Seasonality

e Forest fragmentation index

f Mean Altitude

g Human Footprint Index

h Forest land cover change (2000 – 2018)

i Herbaceous cover

j Density of Wild Boar

k Domestic Pig Density

l Tree or shrub cover

m Arable land and permanent crop cover change (2000 – 2018)

n Mosaic natural vegetation (>50%)

o Tree cover, mixed leaf

p Grassland

q Mosaic tree and shrub (>50%)

r Bioregion

s Tree cover, needle leaved (>15%)

t Cropland

u Mosaic cropland (>50%)

v Urban areas

w Distance to the nearest road

x Suitability for Wild Boar

y Distance to nearest grid cell with wild boar

Figure 5a – y. Partial dependence plots showing the effect that each of the predictor variables is predicted to have on the probability of ASF occurring in a given region. See Table 2 for a full description of each variable.

3.1.3 Persistence (1)

By removing the potential effects of spatial patterning amongst ASF-cases and ASF-negative reports, the ASF persistence model indicated that, amongst the original 23 environmental predictors and the probability of ASF occurrence, only 11 predictors are likely to have an effect, with the remaining 13 registering as “unimportant” (Table 6). Of the two categorical predictors, only LyLPresenc was found to have a statistically significant effect when predicting the persistence of ASF ($p < 0.05$; Table 6). For the continuous, smoothed predictors, ASF_Suitability, bio3, bio9, bio18 and road_distance, were shown to be statistically significant ($p < 0.05$ for all; Table 6).

Table 6. A summary of model outputs for categorical and continuous predictors, indicating the strength and direction (coefficient) and statistical significance (p-value) of each variable in predicting the probability of ASF persistence in Latvia and Lithuania. Estimates are a product of a generalised additive model, in which all predictors were included, along with an intrinsic selection process to remove those variables which had little to no effect on model performance/predictions.

Type of Predictor	Predictor	Coefficient	Z-value	P-value
Categorical	LyLPresenc: Presence of Eurasian lynx	-1.083	-2.501	0.012
	UrAPresenc: Presence of Brown bear	-0.406	-0.793	0.428

Continuous	alt*: Mean Altitude	9.396×10^{-6}	0.000	0.437
	arable_change*: Arable land and permanent crop cover change (2000–2018)	1.282×10^{-5}	0.000	0.616
	ASF_Suitability: output of occurrence model	4.334	131.866	< 0.001
	bio3: Isothermality - areas with relative constant temperature	0.747	3.712	0.021
	bio8: Mean Temperature of Wettest Quarter	0.841	1.866	0.087
	bio9: Mean Temperature of Driest Quarter	0.767	3.914	0.018
	bio10*: Mean Temperature of Warmest Quarter	1.291×10^{-5}	0.000	0.867
	bio15*: Precipitation Seasonality	1.118×10^{-5}	0.000	0.995
	bio18: Precipitation of Warmest Quarter	1.629	7.173	0.007
	connectivity_distance*: Distance to nearest grid cell with known wild boar presence	5.132×10^{-5}	0.000	0.270
	DA_PigDensity*: Domestic Pig Density	1.131×10^{-5}	0.000	0.946
	density*: Density of Wild Boar	8.668×10^{-6}	0.000	0.956
	ffi*: Forest fragmentation index	1.068×10^{-5}	0.000	0.744
	forest_change*: Forest land cover change (2000 – 2018)	1.671×10^{-5}	0.000	0.494
	Hfp: Human Footprint Index	0.596	1.739	0.078
	lc11*: Herbaceous cover	1.586×10^{-5}	0.000	0.493
	lc30*: Mosaic cropland (>50%)	1.091×10^{-5}	0.000	0.748
	lc60: Tree cover deciduous (>15%)	0.440	0.792	0.152
	lc90*: Tree cover, mixed leaf	9.436×10^{-6}	0.000	0.985
	lc180: Shrub or herbaceous cover, flooded	0.420	1.052	0.108
road_distance: Distance to nearest road	0.683	2.695	0.044	

	sun*: Solar radiation inferred	7.018×10^{-6}	0.000	0.768
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Note: **Bold** indicates those environmental predictor variables for which a statistically significant effect, at 95% significance level ($\alpha = 0.05$) was identified. Asterisks (*) denote those variables which have been deemed as unimportant by the GAM's intrinsic selection process, having had their smoothing term penalised to zero (as reflected in their Chi-square value), effectively removing them from the model.

Evaluation of the GAM outputs, along with associated partial dependence plots (Figure 6a – i), revealed potential issues with regards to the fitting of hfp, lc60 and lc180; likely a result of the skewed distribution of datapoints within the landscape (see Figure 6f, g, i). Attempts were made to improve the fit of these predictors by penalising the smoothing term for each however, these issues continued to persist. The systematic removal of these variables (individually and in combination) did little to improve model performance when compared to the original model as indicated by the Akaike Information Criterion (AIC; 263.716 – full model; 265.044 – removal of hfp; 263.487 – removal of lc60; 263.781 – removal of lc180; 266.359 – removal of hfp and lc60; 266.732 – removal of hfp and lc180; 265.373 – removal of lc60 and lc180; 266.512 – removal of hfp, lc60 and lc180). As such, the original model was considered the most appropriate.

a

b

c

d

e

f

g

h

i

Figure 6. Visualization of the GAM outputs. The plots show the nonlinear effect of relevant predictor variables.

The strongest predictor of persistence is the output from the occurrence model. This suggests that areas where ASF is most likely to occur first, will also be the areas where it is most likely to persist. These results also indicate that persistence appears to be reduced in the presence on Lynx as a predator and scavenger. For future work it may be useful to combine mammalian predator density, rather than treat them individually, as some will not be present in specific countries. The importance of numerous factors indicate that climate is influencing disease persistence, alongside the increasing distance from roads. Land cover and land use (change) factors other than distance to roads did not contribute significantly to persistence.

Using the ASF persistence model, predicting to the full extent of Latvia and Lithuania revealed a number of regions in which, based on the probability of ASF occurrence and a sub-selection of environmental predictors, ASF might persist long-term (Figure 7a,b).

a

b

Figure 7. The modelled persistence of ASF in (a) Latvia, (b) Lithuania. Insets shows the ASF-cases (from Figure 1).

3.1.4 Persistence (2)

The minimum adequate model (MAM) for the ASF persistence model, saw the retention of 35 risk variables in explaining variations in the number of repeated outbreaks in regions of Latvia and Lithuania. Four variables (lc71, lc150, lc202, and suitability) were systematically removed, without having a significant effect on model fit (p -value > 0.05).

Of those variables retained, many were predicted to have a statistically significant effect on persistence (Table 7). Similarly, those landscape variables relating to semi-natural habitat types, particularly deciduous (lc60 and lc61) or mixed-leaf woodland (lc90) were also shown to have an effect; although this appeared to be in relation to the presence of semi-natural habitat (i.e. coverage), rather than changes in land use practices (e.g. agricultural expansion). All variables relating to potential barriers (excluding permanent snow/ice; lc220), were found to show a statistically significant negative effect on ASF persistence, such as forest fragmentation (ffi), and the presence of or proximity to anthropogenic features (e.g. roads), or waterbodies. Predicted wild boar density was not significant, and domestic pig density had a negative association with persistence.

As with the ASF occurrence model, climatic variables relating to temperature (bio3, bio8, bio9, and bio10) and precipitation (bio13 and bio15) were predicted to have a statistically significant effect on ASF persistence ($p < 0.05$ for all).

Table 7. Summary outputs of the ASF Persistence Model, describing the model coefficient, z-value and p-value for all variables retained in the minimum adequate model.

Risk Variable	Coefficient	Z-value	P-value
Alt: Mean Altitude	-7.183e-04	-0.077	0.938
arable_change: Arable land and permanent crop cover change (2000 – 2018)	1.286e-03	-1.195	0.232
bio10: Mean Temperature of Warmest Quarter	-3.332e-01	2.663	0.008
bio13: Precipitation of Wettest Month	-8.753e-02	-4.847	<0.001
bio15: Precipitation Seasonality	1.319e-01	-16.939	<0.001
bio3: Isothermality, areas with relative constant temperature	1.262e-01	13.196	<0.001
bio8: Mean Temperature of Wettest Quarter	-1.091e-01	6.863	<0.001
bio9: Mean Temperature of Driest Quarter	-1.137e-01	-7.756	<0.001
Bioregion: Bioclimatic region	-2.020e-01	-8.979	0.395
Connectivity_distance: Distance to nearest grid cell with known wild boar presence	-1.027e-01	-0.851	<0.001
DA_PigDensity: Domestic Pig Density	-7.349e-04	-7.828	<0.001
Density: Density of Wild Boar	-2.621e-02	-11.627	0.138
Ffi: Forest fragmentation index	3.587	-1.484	<0.001
Forest_change: Forest land cover change (2000 – 2018)	7.969e-04	5.622	0.076
Grow: Length of Vegetation Growing Period	4.688e-03	1.777	0.733
Hfp: Human Footprint Index	-4.234e-03	0.341	0.043
lc10: Cropland	-2.697e-03	-2.029	0.026
lc100: Mosaic tree and shrub (>50%)	1.996e-02	-2.222	<0.001
lc11: Herbaceous cover	1.012e-03	5.052	0.511
lc110: Mosaic herbaceous cover (>50%)	5.127e-02	0.657	0.464
lc12: Tree or shrub cover	3.939e-02	0.732	0.198
lc130: Grassland	7.845e-04	1.286	0.688
lc180: Shrub or herbaceous cover, flooded	-1.361e-02	0.402	0.002
lc190: Urban areas	-5.598e-02	-3.102	<0.001
lc210: Water bodies	-2.025e-02	-3.597	<0.001
lc30: Mosaic cropland (>50%)	6.748e-03	-5.353	<0.001
lc40: Mosaic natural vegetation (>50%)	-3.567e-02	4.677	0.025
lc60: Tree cover, deciduous (>15%)	1.698e-02	-2.236	<0.001
lc61: Tree cover, deciduous (>40%)	-2.020e-01	17.629	<0.001
lc80: Tree cover, needle leaved, deciduous, (>15%)	-8.867e-01	-5.664	0.144
lc90: Tree cover, mixed	7.010e-03	-1.463	<0.001
Presence: Wild boar presence (categorical)	-2.285e-01	5.976	<0.001

Range: Range of stable long-term populations	1.520e+01	-4.470	0.886
Road_distance: Distance to the nearest road	-1.006e-02	0.143	<0.001
Sun: Solar radiation inferred	-1.726e-04	-4.978	0.180

Note: **Bold** indicates those environmental predictor variables for which a statistically significant effect, at 95% significance level ($\alpha = 0.05$) was identified.

4 Conclusions and recommendations

ASF continues to expand in Europe in both domestic pigs and wild boar (EFSA et al, 2024). A review of the analysis of ASF cases (EFSA et al., 2022) identified habitat characteristics (suitable vegetation), socio-economic factors (human footprint index) and wild boar density as risk factors. However, some of the analyses reviewed looked at positive cases at a relatively low resolution (e.g. NUTS3 or LAU). The four analyses conducted here used the highest resolution data for positive cases and negative results, which limited the geographic area over which the analyses could be conducted but should give an improved chance of finding locally important risk factors.

For the occurrence of ASF the analyses agree that climatic factors were the most important (precipitation of warmest quarter; mean temperature of wettest quarter; precipitation seasonality), with temperature (including solar radiation) and rainfall as the four most important factors in both analyses. Domestic pig density was moderately important in both analyses, and wild boar density only moderately important in the second (ASF occurrence in the first year of the outbreak). Mean altitude, forest fragmentation, human footprint index and other habitat factors were moderately important. A more detailed look at the most important factors for ASF occurrence in wild boar (Figs 3, 5) indicates the very non-linear nature of these factors, with many having a threshold above which the risk increases (or decreases) by a few percent.

While several factors appeared to be important for the occurrence of ASF cases, the relationship with risk is non-linear and may appear different in each model. Both occurrence models identified precipitation (in the warmest quarter, bio18; and seasonal variation, bio8), mean temperature in the wettest quarter, forest fragmentation, altitude and domestic pig density in the top list of factors. The inclusion of additional countries in the second analysis elevated the importance of daily temperature range (bio2) but removed solar radiation (sun) as an important factor. Additionally, the importance of predicted wild boar density became moderately significant, probably because this parameter had an increased range of values. Thus, these analyses suggest that climate, altitude and forest fragmentation are important for ASF occurrence in the modelled scenario.

Most of these variables are likely to contribute to persistence of ASF virus in the environment, although they may indirectly contribute to risks of infection. The density of one predator (lynx) was associated with a decrease in persistence of ASF in the first model, and further analysis should examine the combined effects of mammalian or avian predators to reduce the effect of changing species distribution across Europe. This can be a correlational finding mediated by ecological factors and management determining presence of lynx in low ASF risk areas and not a direct effect, which requires further analysis.

For the persistence of ASF, the first model indicated that ASF occurrence was the most important factor. Since this may be circular reasoning, the second analysis, looking at duration of ASF cases, did not include this. However, this had to be a linear model to work, and many factors may not be linear (as indicated above). This indicated a high number of statically important factors, which included again climatic factors such as precipitation and temperature, along with habitat. Habitat features are difficult to summarise, as mosaic cropland (>50%), forest fragmentation and mosaic tree cover increase risk, but too much tree cover, cropland, water bodies and urban areas decrease risk. Domestic pig density had a negative effect only in the second analysis number of quarters with ASF, and wild boar density had no effect. Two factors had competing influences between the two models: i.e. distance to road had a positive influence in the first model but a negative influence in the second; mean temperature of the driest quarter was positive in the first, and negative in the second. Many factors were only significant in one of the two analyses, so we have to conclude that there are no strong drivers of disease persistence in the areas of study. This may be due to the limited variation experienced in the two countries, and that further analyses using much wider geographical scope may well determine which factors drive persistence across other parts of Europe.

One way to interpret these combined results, is that ASF in wild boar is not driven by a simple relationship with presence or density, but in combination with habitat features that promote wild boar connectivity (such as a mosaic habitat) and a climate that promotes infectivity (of individuals or carcasses). It is likely that the limited geographical extent of the available data also limited the results and conclusions that can be drawn.

Therefore, the most important conclusion from this work is that insufficient geographically precise data on ASF reports have been collected across Europe. ASF in wild boar has been reported in at least 18 countries in Europe over the last few years. However, we could only access high quality geo-referenced positive and negative ASF data for Latvia, Lithuania, Italy, Sweden and Belgium, and the limited geographic extent of cases in Italy, Sweden and Belgium meant that it was difficult to use these data, since the removal of spatial autocorrelation left few data points. It is therefore vitally important that wildlife disease data are collected accurately, are readily available, and include negative reports as a measure of effort and to infer probability of local disease extinction, if future analyses are to improve our understanding of ASF disease dynamics.

ASF positive and negative reports from Latvia and Lithuania were considered sufficiently precise and extensive for initial analyses to examine the occurrence and persistence of ASF in wild boar. Data from Sweden and Italy were only added for the second occurrence model due to data thinning to avoid spatial autocorrelation.

These results could be used with another approach to develop a spatio-temporal spread model (e.g. MIGCLIM; Engler et al., 2012), to calculating the probability of local transmission from areas of persistence to novel regions based on landscape suitability.

Overall, the findings are also in agreement with other work (e.g. Zakharova et al. 2024) that wild boar density may not be of overriding importance, and that forest cover and domestic pig density are important factors, but this work also identified many climatic factors which were not previously reported (EFSA et al. 2022).

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